

Case study on toolkit advocacy focus groups

Data Archive: Lithuanian Data Archive for Humanities and Social Sciences (LiDA)

Introduction

This case study reports on testing in focus groups of the emerging cost-benefit advocacy toolkit during 2016. It also presents an analysis of the discussion and feedback from the Lithuanian focus groups.

It is based on two focus groups conducted in May 2016, one with staff from the Lithuanian Data Archive for Social Sciences and Humanities (LiDA), and the other with representatives from its key stakeholders including its funders.

LiDA is a single-site social science data service established in 2006 by Kaunas University of Technology in partnership with Vilnius University, the Institute for Social Research, and the Ministry of Education and Science of the Republic of Lithuania.

In January 2011 LiDA was recognized as a national research infrastructure and was included in the Roadmap for Research Infrastructures of Lithuania. LiDA has been a member of the Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives (CESSDA) since 2013.

Today LiDA is responsible for the acquisition and dissemination of national and international data sets, data access to international data archives, data analysis training and publication of data analysis teaching materials. Study descriptions are documented bilingually in English and Lithuanian, which makes the data sets potentially of interest for the international community.

LiDA development was funded by the Ministry of Education and Science and EU Structural funds.

LiDA has:

- over **400 datasets**
- over **2000 registered users**

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Focus Group Testing of the CESSDA-SaW Toolkit

Over the two weeks 16-27 May 2016 nine focus groups were held in Finland, Estonia, Slovenia and Lithuania as part of CESSDA SaW task 4.6 developing a funding advocacy toolkit. The focus groups were led by Charles Beagrie Ltd and hosted and facilitated by staff in each country. The focus groups were of two types: for staff from the social science data archive exploring results of the user requirements survey (see the Task 4.6 Cost-Benefit Advocacy Toolkit Deliverable Report for further details of the survey) and emerging ideas for the toolkit; and for their key stakeholders (typically senior staff from the host university, government ministries, national statistics offices, representative researchers and depositors) presenting economic approaches to the value and impact of social science data archives and emerging content for the toolkit.

The Staff Focus Groups

One two-hour staff focus group was held in each country. Feedback reinforced findings from the user requirements survey and confirmed positive direction and emerging ideas for the toolkit. Notes from the sessions were used to help further refine and develop the emerging tools.

The Key Stakeholder Focus Groups

These varied from 1 to 1.5 hours in length with sessions being kept shorter to attract the maximum number of senior participants from key stakeholders. Participants ranged from 3-11 people per focus group depending on local requirements and invitation. As well as providing feedback on the emerging toolkit, the stakeholder focus groups in themselves proved useful for advocacy on behalf of social science data archives in their respective countries. There was a high-level of active engagement and questions. An exit evaluation form was completed to capture feedback anonymously and individual comments were also captured in meeting notes to help shape the final toolkit.

The CESSDA SaW Cost-Benefit Advocacy Toolkit Focus Groups in Lithuania

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The Lithuanian focus groups were held in Kaunas on 27th of May, 2016. Each group was given a brief introduction to previous work on measuring value and impact of research data infrastructure, with particular reference to the ESDS impact study (Beagrie et al 2012). This was followed by an overview of the toolkit user requirements survey results, and proposals for the toolkit components and content. There was then time for extensive discussion. The feedback forms and the meeting notes from all of the focus groups were used later to help shape and finalise the toolkit.

It was noted that social sciences in Lithuania are fragmented as there are 50 different institutions working in this area and they each do their own research, so a central archive was felt to be very important.

It was also noted it has always been a problem to measure the value and impact of social sciences. For the Lithuania focus group participants, assessing the impact of social science research data services using economic approaches was relatively a new concept compared to other approaches such as tracking citations.

The Staff Focus Group

Lithuania staff and faculty focus group, May 2016

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The first focus group was for staff and faculty, and there were six attendees. The faculty includes Psychology, Sociology, Political Science and Anthropology as well as other Social Sciences, and has developed interdisciplinary social work programmes.

Staff concerns in Lithuania were focused on long term funding for sustainability, ensuring data quality and getting consensus on data reuse. The toolkit was seen as very helpful in providing easy to digest and apply approaches and evidence to support staff in advocacy on these issues.

The Key Stakeholder Focus Group

Lithuania stakeholders focus group, May 2016

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The second focus group was for representatives of key stakeholders, and there were 11 attendees. The stakeholders present consisted of research data users, research data producers, and representatives of decision-makers and funders.

Feedback forms were distributed at the end of the key stakeholders' focus group, and the results of free-text and pre-set scaled responses from these have been summarised in the following charts. Overall the positive reception of the toolkit and the strong interest in the topics discussed mirrored that of the other focus groups held elsewhere as part of the toolkit testing.

Lithuania stakeholder focus group:
Would the toolkit change your perceptions of social science research data impact in any way?
 (n=11)

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Lithuania stakeholder focus group feedback:
How would you rate today's focus group?

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Discussion, key suggestions, and lessons

The Toolkit

- Strong interest was expressed in applying the final toolkit within Lithuania. It was seen as fit for purpose and relevant for its target audience.
- Participants felt it was also important to consider the wider impact such as for policy makers, social workers, Non-Governmental Organisations, and education providers. The toolkit could be useful in many other contexts.
- The focus groups were very successful in providing feedback to confirm and help finalise the emerging toolkit. In addition, the focus group with key stakeholders in Lithuania helped to engage them with the issues and evidence being gathered – in itself this was a valuable part of the advocacy programme.

Data reuse

- Retaining data would help students not to have to conduct so many surveys and helps combat survey fatigue among the target population.
- Participants said they would think more about reusing instruments and data in future.

Resistance to data sharing

- Researchers want to use international data but may resist sharing their own data, for reasons of protection of their IP. The legal landscape is very important.
- There is a need to improve incentives in order to change the academic mindset.

Mandating deposit as a condition of funding

- Policies may take a while to embed in practice and culture. Mandating deposit is a good start. In Lithuania it has been policy since 2009 that every dataset created using public money should be given to the national archive and after some initial resistance there is now greater acceptance of this idea.
- A research funder may stipulate a minimum retention period. Costs may also be a consideration.

National strategy and policy

- Strategy and policy at a national level is an important basis for funding and long term sustainability.
- Cost benefit analysis in social sciences depends on long term sustainability – it takes many years to build-up impact and for it to be visible and measured.

Standards and good practice

- Standards and trust are important. All data should be retained for later validation, but data for use in policy needs to be of good enough quality and needs to be well curated.
- There is a need to ensure that there is no duplication in access to the same datasets from other gateways.
- Participants were interested in examples of good practice from other countries and tools for data analysis competence building.

Big data

- The definition of big data may be discipline-specific – in the humanities it is often about digitisation of existing resources. For social sciences it is more quantitative. Only science is producing huge datasets. However, some of the smaller datasets are richer in information.
- There are opportunistic corpora of data which when they reach critical mass can be usefully mined with

the use of technology. There is a need to explain that the added value is getting *knowledge* out of *data*.

- Big data is about data analysis skills and interdisciplinary study. It can be mined and combined in new ways for added value. The public/private partnership is important here.

Economic impact

- Do not to do a cost-benefit analysis too early but it is a good idea to have long term statistics to show when usage takes off.

The costs of inaction

- The cost of inaction (i.e. implications of not having a central archive but relying on personal requests to data creators) in terms of obtaining data for reuse is probably much harsher for people lower down the academic pecking order. It is very expensive to reproduce datasets like census data, so access is very important particularly for doctoral students.
- It would be a good idea to repeat the Wicherts study (Wicherts et al 2006) on the costs of inaction in other disciplines which are also orientated to empirical research. Costs of inaction are discussed in the toolkit (see Return on Investment Factsheet). Further research in this area was seen in the focus groups as potentially a high priority for future work.

Linked toolkit resources

Effort

User Guide, <http://dx.doi.org/10.18448/16.0001>

Return on Investment Factsheet, <http://dx.doi.org/10.18448/16.0002>

D4.9 Cost-benefit Advocacy Toolkit Deliverable Report, <http://dx.doi.org/10.18448/16.0011>

Other Linked resources

Lithuanian Data Archive for Social Sciences (LiDA), <http://www.lidata.eu/>.

References

Beagrie, N., Houghton, J., Palaiologk, A., and Williams, P., 2012, *Economic Impact Evaluation of the Economic and Social Data Service*, <http://www.esrc.ac.uk/files/research/evaluation-and-impact/economic-impact-evaluation-of-the-economic-and-social-data-service/>

Wicherts, J.M., Borsboom, D., Kats, J., and Molenaar, D. , 2006, The poor availability of psychological research data for reanalysis, *American Psychologist*, Volume 61 Issue7 pgs726-8, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/0003-066X.61.7.726>